

Remote Enrollment System in Public Elementary Schools in Pililla Sub - Office

Nessie Meg V. Masinsin

Abstract:- Remote Enrollment System was first conducted in the Philippines during the school year 2020-2021 as a response to the challenges brought by the Covid 19 pandemic. The purpose of this research is to examine the status of implementation of remote enrollment system in meeting the current demands of the educational system and its stakeholders and to determine the perception of the teacher and parent respondents with regards to the implementation of the remote enrollment system. Further, the researcher utilized descriptive research design to assess the feedback of 281 elementary school teachers and 81 parents in terms of the system's goals and objectives, enrollment procedure, health and safety, enrollment materials, monitoring and evaluation and data privacy. It has been revealed that teachers perceived that Remote Enrollment System was very much implemented. On the other hand, Remote Enrollment System was much implemented as perceived by the parent respondents.

Keywords:- Remote Enrollment System, Covid – 19, Goals And Objectives, Enrollment Procedure, Health and Safety, Enrollment Materials, Monitoring And Evaluation and Data Privacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Amidst the continuing health threat, it cannot be denied that education system OF the Philippines is one of the most affected sectors of the society. To cope up with the changing and rough times that all Filipinos were currently facing, the Department of Education (DepEd) designed the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) to make sure that learning continues while taking into consideration the health, safety, and well-being of all learners and DepEd personnel. The LCP introduces the multiple learning delivery modalities such as blended learning, distance learning, and homeschooling to reach all learners from differing backgrounds and remote areas. Still, learners' enrollment is crucial to be able to formally access the educational opportunities. Nevertheless, the enrollment and data gathering procedures must take into consideration the health and protection of teachers and learners.

Consequently, they introduced the remote enrollment system under the new normal of education to lessen the physical interaction among the parents, learners, teachers and other personnel to minimize risks of transmission of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) amidst the pandemic. Also, the Department of Education reiterated that the enrollment will mainly be conducted through remote enrollment which means that enrollment will be done through online processes such as submission of Learner Enrollment and Survey Form (LESF)

through texts, Facebook and other alternative ways of communication.

In public schools, the admission period for the school year 2020-2021 begun on June 1, 2020. However, unlike previous years, parents or guardians can now enroll their children without leaving a safe home. This means that the Learner Enrollment and Survey Forms (LESF) will be collected through the most convenient system between teachers and parents, such as Facebook messengers, text messages, or survey management software (such as Google Form). In addition, Learner Enrollment and Survey Forms (LESF) should be collected this school year to obtain information related to the ability to assess the basic education system and appropriate student goals to continue to provide learning this school year while implementing the physical distancing measures as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic.

II. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey method was used to attain the objective of this study. According to Calmorin (2016) the descriptive method focuses on the present, the "what is" of the situation with the purpose to seek "new truth". Hence, the study was descriptive survey in nature because it involves the collection of data using a questionnaire-checklist administered to the respondents after which it was treated with appropriate statistical tools to determine their responses.

The study was conducted in nine (9) public elementary schools in Pililla Sub-office. These schools are composed of Bugarin Elementary School, Halayhayin Elementary School, Hulo Elementary School, Malaya Elementary School, Matagbak Elementary School, Niogan Elementary School, Pililla Elementary School Central, Quisao Elementary School and Virgilio B. Melendres Memorial Elementary School.

The respondents of the study were the 281 public elementary school teachers and 81 General Parent-Teacher Association (GPTA) Officers of Pililla Sub-office. Purposive sampling technique was used. They were described in terms of their age, sex, civil status, position title, length of service, educational attainment, webinars and trainings attended, monthly family income, number of children in the family and occupation. Descriptive survey research design was used. A researcher-made questionnaire-checklist was utilized to assess the implementation of Remote Enrollment System in public elementary schools with respect to goals and objectives, enrollment procedure, health and safety, enrollment materials, monitoring and evaluation and data privacy. Problems encountered in the implementation of Remote Enrollment System were also determined.

After several revisions on the questionnaire based on the suggestion of the educational management experts, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study and to distribute the questionnaires. After the approval was secured, the questionnaires were administered to the respondents through Google Forms. Data Privacy Agreement was included in the Form. After retrieving, the questionnaires were tallied, computed, analyzed and interpreted.

The following scale was used:

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	
5	4.50 – 5.00	Very Much Implemented	Very Much Serious
4	3.50 – 4.49	Much Implemented	Much Serious
3	2.50 – 3.49	Implemented	Serious
2	1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Implemented	Less Serious
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not Implemented	Not Serious

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This portion analyzes and discusses the findings of the study. Moreover, it interprets the gathered data based from the perception of teachers and parents on the implementation of Remote Enrollment System.

A. Profile of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Civil Status, Position Title, Length of Service, Educational Attainment and Webinars and Trainings Attended and Parent-Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Civil Status, Monthly Family Income, Number of Children in the Family and Occupation

- The teacher-respondents are mostly on their maturity ages and predominantly females with most of them are married; in teacher I position; have been in the service for 21 years and above; most of them have highest educational attainment of bachelor’s degree and mainly attended webinars and trainings related to enrollment in division level. Further, the parent-respondents are mainly 41 years old and above mostly female with majority of them are married; have a monthly family income of 10,000 and below; primarily have 2-3 children in the family and mainly are housewife or househusband.

B. Status of Implementation of the Remote Enrollment System as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with Respect to Goals and Objectives, Enrollment Procedure, Health and Safety, Enrollment Materials, Monitoring and Evaluation and Data Privacy

- The teacher Remote Enrollment System is very much implemented with respect to goals and objectives, enrollment procedure, health and safety, enrollment materials, monitoring and evaluation and data privacy as evaluated by teacher respondents. Nonetheless, the parent-respondents perceived that the Remote Enrollment System is much implemented with respect to goals and objectives, enrollment procedure, health

and safety, enrollment materials, monitoring and evaluation and data privacy.

C. Significant Difference Between the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Status of Implementation of Remote Enrollment System with Respect to the Cited Aspects

- There is a significant difference exists between the perception of the teacher and parent respondents on the implementation of Remote Enrollment System with respect to goals and objectives, enrollment procedure, health and safety, enrollment materials, monitoring and evaluation and data privacy.

D. Significant Difference on the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Status of Implementation of Remote Enrollment System with Respect to the Cited Aspects in Terms of their Profile

- There is no significant difference exists on the perception of teacher respondents on the implementation of Remote Enrollment System in terms of their age, sex, civil status, position title and webinars and trainings attended with respect to goals and objectives, enrollment procedure, health and safety, enrollment materials, monitoring and evaluation and data privacy, however, in terms of their length of service and educational attainment, there is a significant difference exist. On the other side, there is no significant difference exists on the perception of parent-respondents on the implementation of Remote Enrollment System in terms of their age, sex, monthly family income, number of children in the family and occupation with respect to goals and objectives, enrollment procedure, health and safety, enrollment materials, monitoring and evaluation and data privacy, but, in terms of their civil status there is a significant difference exist.

E. Problems Encountered by the Two Groups of Respondents on the Implementation of the Remote Enrollment System

- The most common problems encountered by the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Remote Enrollment System are “Parents don’t have their own gadget to enroll their child online”, “Difficulty in reaching those pupils who live in far and isolated area” and “Teachers and parents lack of knowledge in technology and social media which are the main approach to communicate”. Comparatively, parent-respondents inferred that “Difficulty in reaching those pupils who live in far and isolated area”, “Parents don’t have their own gadget to enroll their child online” and “Parents were not willing to enroll their child due to fear of Covid-19 transmission”

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

- Age, Sex, Civil Status, Position Title and Webinars and Trainings Attended taught have no bearing on the perception of the teachers on the implementation of Remote Enrollment System but Length of Service and Educational Attainment have bearing on some aspects.
- Age, Sex, Monthly Family Income, Number of Children in the Family and Occupation have no bearing on the perception of the parents on the implementation of Remote

Enrollment System but Civil Status have bearing on some aspects.

RECOMMENDATION

In the light of the findings, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

- Orientation of varied enrollment systems should be planned and implemented to familiarize the teachers, parents and learners on the enrollment processes.
- The schools should provide Personal Protective Equipment's (PPE's) for teachers assigned on enrollment kiosks.
- Disinfection of classrooms, enrollment kiosks and other physical facilities should be done regularly to guarantee the health and safety of all stakeholders.
- Disinfection of enrollment forms and documents is recommended to ensure that it will not carry any virus.
- Different modes and activities in Remote Enrollment System should be continuously implemented to all learners to enable them to have access to education amidst the pandemic.
- Schools should have a clear guidelines regarding the new enrollment policy such as the need to fill out the Learner Enrollment and Survey Form (LESF).
- The proposed action plan is recommended for implementation.
- Similar studies may be conducted considering other variables.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Nollado, Jose N., Philippine Constitution, Article XIV, Section 2, Manila: National Bookstore.
- [2]. Calmorin, Laurentina P. (2016). Research and Thesis Writing with Statistics Computer Application. Manila: Rex Bookstore.
- [3]. Briones, Leonora M., (2020) Guidelines on Enrollment for School Year 2020- 2021 in the Context of the Public Health Emergency due to Covid 19.
- [4]. www.deped.gov.ph/2020/05/28/do-008-s-2020.
- [5]. Ching, Jorge. (2020). "PH Education and the New Normal", *Philippine Inquirer*.
- [6]. Malipot – Henando, Merlina. (2020). "DepEd to Implement Remote Enrollment This June, *Manila Bulletin*.